

Demographic Variables Influencing Care of Elderly in Nupeland, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study investigated demographic variables influencing care of elderly in Nupeland, Nigeria. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The study population consisted of all elderly people above 65 years old in Nupeland in Kwara, Kogi and Niger States. The sample size for this study consisted of 581 elderly people above 65 years old from Nupe tribe in Nupeland in Kwara, Kogi and Niger States. The sample was selected using multi stage sampling procedure. Care of Elderly Questionnaire (CEQ) was used to collect relevant data for the study and it was administered on the elderly people. The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by experts in Health Education, and Tests, Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was analysed using Cronbach Alpha. Co-efficient value of 0.79 for CEQ was obtained and considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. The responses obtained was collated and analysed using descriptive statistics while the hypotheses postulated were subjected to inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance and t-test. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland was moderate. Also, there was no difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status, religion and gender. It was recommended among others that Government should implement the regular evaluation of elderly care so to serve as evidence base for improved quality care services for the elderly

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Introduction

The varying privileges of ageing people in the contemporary society tends to place them in an unhappy condition as they are fronting the challenges of paucity, malnutrition, physical and psychological condition, transportation problem, shelter problem, isolation and thought of death anxiety. In Nigeria, including Nupeland, the ageing appears to suffer a lot of hardship in our contemporary society. They appear to constitute the poorest group in the society, as there was noticeable evidence of penury and begging among them, especially in rural communities where majority of them resides. A cursory look at the implementation of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by the Federal Government of Nigeria shows that there was no consideration for this vulnerable population group. This poses a big problem (Ayenibiowo, Kehinde, Obashoro-John & Ayeni, 2014).

The populace of the ageing people is universally increasing fast and the rate of increase is greater in developing countries including Nigeria. Presently, Nigeria has the uppermost number of the ageing people in Africa. The traditional Nupe culture has ways of taking care of the aged. For example, their extended family and children are expected to make available for them (Abdulraheem & Parakoyi, 2005). Young people in the immediate environment are supposed to help them run errands whether the head are their relative or not. It seems that these types of caring are fast becoming a thing of the past.

Nupe family structure is changing, although the family is an institution which is not disappearing, rather, families are responding and adapting to new conditions, while grown-up persons are adopting new roles within the families. The researcher observed that Nupe family structures are changing and traditional patterns of care seems to be no longer guaranteed.

Communication with some of the aged by the researcher had shown feeling of rejection by some health professionals. This seclusion in an environment where there is no social security for this progressively vulnerable group and the progressive disintegration of extended family system seems to pose serious danger to the psychosocial welfare of the aged and graceful ageing, therefore huge public health problems and concern (Fajemilehin & Odebiyi, 2011).

The researcher observed that grown-up people were highly respected and adequately taken care of by their extended family system. However, as the society reforms the traditional lifestyle of taking care of grown-up people has changed. It appears that changes in the structure of the society leaves elder people with many challenges in the hand of health professionals. With this upsurge in the growth of the ageing population, the number of people that will need health care will undoubtedly increase.

In old age, weight loss is now more certain and as the body dries up and the subcutaneous fats disappears, the skin becomes dehydrated and wrinkled and the eyes sunken. Bristle bones whilst teeth becomes decay and loosen. Movement becomes slow, awkward and difficult. Subsequently, people in Nigeria today are afraid of old age and are beginning to see it as an age of increasing tension and anxiety. The trials facing the ageing people are largely a social creation. These challenges are exacerbated by the existence of ageism. Majority of them were unemployed since they were young. These aged people lived in extreme poverty and cannot provide their daily needs. Having retired from labour, especially

few of them that managed to get jobs, they may be poorer than ever before in their lives (Harrefos, 2009; Lecovich, 2008).

Some obituary posters with such captions as “A glorious exit,” or “A life well spent,” are reflections of the quality of life the departed had enjoyed. This however appears not the case for many Nigerians who died through poverty and institutional neglect. With growing numbers of grown-up people in Nigeria, unfortunately the rise is taking place in a situation where the society is least prepared for challenges that older people are presenting. The range of problems that grown-up people are facing is continually increasing as societies are locked up in conflicts, experience huge economic problems, natural disasters, diseases and deterioration in family relationships.

Care of the ageing is the fulfilment of the special needs and requirements that are unique to senior citizens. It covers such services as assisted living, adult day care, long term care and home care. Elderly care stresses the social and personal requirements of senior citizens who need some assistance with daily activities and health care, but who desire to age with dignity. The care of the aged is multidimensional and these include physical, emotional, spiritual and social care (Ayres, 2008; Ercole, 2011). The researcher observed that care of the aged has till date focused on managing protracted disorders rather than on the raise of healthy lifestyle and prevention of chronic diseases. Caring for the aged is a family obligation among the Nupes, it is believed that whoever cared for his/her aged parents will also be care for in his own old age.

Educational factor could influence the care of the aged. It seems that some elderly have limited educational chances to develop positive attitudes toward their aged. The researcher observed that the higher the level of education of the aged, the more positive attitude towards their care. Discoveries have also shown that more educated people hold positive attitude towards their care (Loh, 2006). According to the researcher, it seems that those with high educational status appears to have more achievement in getting care because they classically have access to wide range of information and positive disposition on seeking for health care. They also have easy access to information on proper care method regarding their health, as well as their social, emotional and cognitive development.

Religion was defined as an institutionalized system of attitudes, beliefs and practices to which a person can be labelled as a member, an adherent or an endorser of the related set of tenets, a person's faith was regarded as synonymous with his or her religion. Religion has been detected to be another contributing determinant that could influence the care of elderly. For instance, the 19th century Christian missionaries gave Africans a new worldview that is not mono-sectional (Sijuwade, 2008). The visible world is clearly parted from the invisible world, and after death there are heaven and hell. In this flow of thought, there is no room for ancestral blasphemies or visits from living-dead if you do not care for the elderly.

In recent years, the term ‘religious fundamentalism’ has been commonly used to connect religion with societal roles. What is clearly evident is that each of the two dominant religions observes the care for aged in different perspectives. Suffice is to add that they both view care for the aged as a role that must be done by the younger generations.

Religion and religious activities may have impact on society in two ways. First, religious activities, such as church attendance, are social activities that could be an

instrument for creating networks for economic doings. The impact of religion in transforming people's behaviour cannot be overemphasized. Some religions activities may delay active attention that should be given to the aged people.

Gender refers to the social structures of masculinity and femininity. Masculinity means the qualities, behaviours and attitudes traditionally associated with or deemed appropriate for men; femininity for women (Sijuwade, 2009). While constructions of gender vary between places and change over time, gender is regularly a factor that defines who has access to power, authority and resources. Gender of the aged people could also be a contributing factor that could decide the care gotten by them.

This study therefore investigated demographic variables influencing care of elderly in Nupeland, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland; and
- ii. the difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status, religion and gender.

Research Question

This research question will be raised to guide the study:

1. What is the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status.
2. There is no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their religion.
3. There is no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their gender.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The study population consisted of all elderly people above 65 years old in Nupeland in Kwara, Kogi and Niger States. The sample size for this study consisted of 581 elderly people above 65 years old from Nupe tribe in Nupeland in Kwara, Kogi and Niger States. The sample was selected using multi stage sampling procedure.

A questionnaire designed by the researcher tagged "Care of Elderly Questionnaire (CEQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study. It was administered on the elderly people and it consisted of two sections namely Section A and Section B. *Section A* sought for bio-data of the respondents while *Section B* consisted of 20 items to elicit information on the extent of care received by the elderly people. The instruments adopted 4 point scale of Likert type as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) - 4, Agree (A) - 3, Disagree (D) - 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1.

The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by experts in Health Education, and Tests, Measurement and Evaluation. The instrument was said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter, it claimed to measure. The reliability of the instrument was analysed using Cronbach Alpha. Co-efficient value of 0.79 for CEQ was obtained and considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. The

responses obtained was collated and analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean, standard deviation and graphs, while the hypotheses postulated were subjected to inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance and t-test. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland?

In answering this question, data on care received by the elderly people were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of CEQ (items 1 – 20) in the questionnaire. Extent of care received by the elderly people was presented in table 1

Table 1: Extent of care received by the elderly people

Extent of care received by the elderly people	No of Respondents	Percent age
Low (20.00 – 49.05)	126	21.7
Moderate (49.06 – 58.42)	298	51.3
High (58.43 – 80.00)	157	27.0
Total	581	100

Table 1 revealed the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland. The mean score and standard deviation of the responses were used to determine the levels as either low, moderate or high. The low extent of care received by the elderly people was determined by subtracting the standard deviation from the mean score ($53.74 - 4.69 = 49.05$). The moderate extent of care received by the elderly people was determined by the mean score (53.74) while the high extent of care received by the elderly people was determined by adding the mean score and standard deviation ($53.74 + 4.69 = 58.43$). Therefore, low extent of care received by the elderly people starts from 20.00 to 49.05, the moderate extent starts from 49.06 to 58.42 and the high extent of care received by the elderly people is from 58.43 to 80.00. The findings showed that the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland was moderate. Figure ii further revealed the extent of care received by the elderly people at a glance

Figure i: Bar Chart showing extent of care received by the elderly people

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance for difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	14.253	4	3.563	0.161	.958
Within Groups	12719.981	576	22.083		
Total	12734.234	580			

P > 0.05

The result presented in Table 2 showed that F_{cal} value of 0.161 was not significant because the P value (0.958) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their religion.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance for difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their religion

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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Between Groups	60.389	2	30.195	1.377	.253
Within Groups	12673.845	578	21.927		
Total	12734.234	580			

$P > 0.05$

The result presented in Table 3 showed that F_{cal} value of 1.377 was not significant because the P value (0.253) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their religion.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their gender

Table 4: Difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their gender

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t_{cal}	P
Male	267	53.90	4.52	579	0.761	0.447
Female	314	53.60	4.83			

$P > 0.05$

Table 4 shows that the t_{cal} value of 0.761 was not significant because the P value (0.447) > 0.05 . This implies that null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, there was no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their gender.

Discussion

The extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland was moderate. The probable reason for this finding might be because of the challenges associated with care of the elderly. Caring for an elderly person does not come without challenges for those who give or practice it either by requiring their substances, presence, touch or attention to listen to the elderly. In support of this finding, Okumagba (2011) concluded that 61.36% of the elders received satisfied care support from health professionals and family members.

The findings also revealed that there was no significant difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status, religion and gender. This implies that health professionals did not segregated the care received by elderly people based on their level of education, religious belief and gender. Ayenibiowo, Kehinde, Obashoro-John and Ayeni (2014), Boswell (2012) and Masciadrelli (2014) concluded that care received by elderly people is not subjected to their level of education, culture, religious belief among others.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the extent of care received by the elderly people in Nupeland was moderate. It is further concluded that there was no difference in the care received by elderly people in Nupeland based on their educational status, religion and gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government should implement the regular evaluation of elderly care so to serve as evidence base for improved quality care services for the elderly people.

2. Healthcare professionals should be more present in care by developing active listening skills and be sensitive to the needs of the elders.

References

- Abdulraheem I. S. & Parakoyi D.B. (2005) Improving attitude towards elderly people: Evaluation of an intervention programme for caregivers. *Nigerian Journal Postgraduate Medical*, 4(12), 280-285.
- Ayenibiowo, O., Kehinde O., Obashoro-John, O.A. & Ayeni, O.B. (2014). The Attitude of Nigerian Young Adults and Adolescents to Grandparents: Implications for Care of the Elderly in Nigeria. *Modern Social Science Journal*, 5(2), 56 – 67
- Ayres, C. (2008). Mediators of the relationship between social support and positive health practices among middle adolescents. *Journal of Pediatric Healthcare*, 22(2). 94-102.
- Boswell, S.S. (2012). Old people are cranky: helping professional trainees' knowledge, attitudes, aging anxiety, and interest in working with older adults. *Educational Gerontology*, 38 (7), 465-472.
- Ercole, D. J, (2011). Is caring a health hazard? The mental health and vitality of carers of a person with a disability in Australia. *The Medical Journal of Australia*, 6(7), 61-5.
- Fajemilehin, B. I., and Odebiyi, A. I. (2011). Predictors of elderly person's quality of life and health practices in Nigeria. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 3(7), 245 – 252.
- Harrefos, C. (2009). Elderly people's perception of how they want to be cared for: An interview study with healthy elderly couples in Northern Sweden. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Science*, 23(8), 353-359.
- Lecovich, E. (2008). Care giving burden, community service and quality of life primary caregivers of frail elderly persons. *Journal of Applied Gerontology*, 27(1), 309-330.
- Loh, D. (2006) Attitudes towards caring for older people: Literature review and methodology. *Nursing Older People* 25(3), 22-27.
- Masciadrelli, B.P (2014). I learned that the aging population isn't that much different from me: The final outcomes of a gero-ed bel project. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work*, 57 (1), 24-36.

Okumagba, P.O. (2011). Family support for the elderly in Delta State of Nigeria. *Stud Hom Com Sci.*, 5(1), 21 – 27.

Sijuwade, P.O. (2009). Attitudes towards old age: A study of the self-image of aged. *Kamla-Raj Stud Home Comm Sci*, 3(1), 1-5

Sijuwade, P. O. (2008) Elderly care by family members: Abandonment, abuse and neglect. *The Social Sciences*, 3(8), 542-547.

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